

SEMANTIC AND PRAGMATIC FUNCTIONS OF ABSTRACT NOUNS IN DIGITAL DISCOURSE

Abdurakhmonov Khudoynazar Abdirayimovich

Karshi State Technical University,

Acting Associate Professor of the

Department of “Foreign Languages”

Email: suhratabdurahmonov120@gmail.com

Tel: (99) 081-30-32

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the theoretical foundations of the concept of digital literacy and its linguistic features. It is scientifically proven that the new discourse environment formed on the basis of such features of Internet communication as interactivity, speed and multimodality has a significant impact on the semantic and pragmatic functions of language units. The study focuses on the role of teaching abstract nouns through digital discourse, showing their functions in generalizing complex reality, semantic organization of abstract nouns and expression of social evaluation..

The rapid development of digital technologies in modern society has radically changed the forms of communication and led to the emergence of new research objects in linguistics. The digital communication environment formed on the basis of the Internet, social networks and mobile communication tools is revealing the scope of application, semantic structure and pragmatic functions of language units in a new way. In this regard, the concept of “digital discourse” has been formed as a separate scientific category in modern linguistic research.

Digital discourse is a complex phenomenon that combines not only communicative, but also social and cognitive aspects of the language system, in which language units acquire new functional functions. This study aims to identify this process, in particular, the semantic-pragmatic role of abstract nouns in digital discourse.

In modern linguistics, the close connection of communication forms with the technological environment has led to the formation of new types of discourse. As a result of the widespread use of the Internet, social networks and mobile communication platforms, the concept of digital discourse has been formed as a separate scientific category in linguistic research. This concept involves the study of speech phenomena related to language units arising in the process of virtual communication, their semantic-pragmatic functions, and sociolinguistic factors[1]. Digital discourse is a communication process carried out through technological means, unlike traditional written or oral speech, which is often characterized by such features as interactivity, speed, and multimodality. In discourse theory, the concept of “discourse” is not limited to text, it also encompasses the communicative situation, social context, and the complex of relationships between speech participants. Therefore, in modern

linguistic research, discourse is interpreted as a form of the language system associated with social activity. M.A.K. Halliday and R. Hasan interpret discourse as a communication system formed through semantic connections between text units, and emphasize the important role of means of meaning transmission in this [2]. This theoretical approach also serves as an important methodological basis in the process of digital communication, because in the Internet environment, texts are often short, fragmentary, and fast, but they are semantically connected through certain connection mechanisms. The linguistic nature of digital discourse has been analyzed by many researchers from various aspects. Internet communication is considered a hybrid form of speech that combines the features of oral and written speech. On the one hand, it is carried out in the form of a written text, and on the other hand, it embodies the features of oral speech, such as dialogic interactivity, unpredictability, and rapid response. For this reason, some researchers also describe digital discourse as “both oral and written speech”[3]. Such a communication environment also affects the semantic and pragmatic functions of language units. Another important issue in explaining the theoretical foundations of digital discourse is the process of abstraction of language units. In the Internet environment, users often express complex realities through short and generalized units. This process leads to the active use of abstract nouns in the language system. H.J. Schmidt describes abstract nouns as conceptual units that embody complex semantic content, calling them “shell nouns” or “conceptual shells”[4]. Such units act as a semantic shell that generalizes a specific idea in discourse and is filled with context. For example, the following speech sample found in English social networks shows how abstract nouns work in digital discourse:

The problem with this update is the lack of transparency.

In this sentence, the abstract nouns *problem* and *transparency* generalize a specific reality. They are used as conceptual units that denote not a specific event, but a social assessment or attitude. Such units allow for semantic organization of discourse and concise expression of ideas. A similar phenomenon is observed in the digital communication environment in Uzbek. For example, the following speech pattern found on *Telegram* or *Instagram* platforms is an example of this:

This decision has caused widespread discussion and protest in society.

In this example, abstract nouns such as *decision*, *discussion*, and *protest* represent a social phenomenon through generalized semantic units. These units serve to express a social assessment, process, or attitude, rather than a specific reality.

Another important feature of digital discourse is its sociolinguistic nature. Internet communication is often formed as a result of interaction between different social groups, cultural environments, and language variants. Therefore, in digital discourse, linguistic units are actively used not only within the framework of the linguistic system, but also as a means of social identification. In this process, abstract nouns serve as an important semantic tool for expressing social evaluation, opinion, or ideological attitude. For example, in English *Twitter* discourse, abstract nouns such as *freedom*, *justice*, *rights*, *responsibility* are often used to express political or social relations[5]. These units are often used in connection with a specific ideological or sociopragmatic environment. This situation shows that the semantic content of linguistic units in discourse analysis is closely related to the social environment.

Theoretical description of digital discourse shows that it is an independent linguistic form of the modern communication system. The interactivity, multimodality and global nature of Internet communication create new functional possibilities of language units. From this point of view, the study of digital discourse is an important reality for modern sociolinguistics, discourse analysis and corpus linguistics. It should not be overlooked that digital technologies in the process of modern communication have a significant impact on the systemic functioning of the language system. Internet-based forms of communication not only expand the scope of application of language units, but also change their semantic, pragmatic and structural properties. Therefore, the study of the mechanisms of application of language units in the digital communication environment is one of the important directions of modern discourse research. Determining the linguistic features of digital discourse is especially important, since the communication conditions that arise in this environment form new functional tasks of language units. One of the main linguistic features of digital communication is the interweaving of elements of written and oral speech, in which abbreviations and multimodal elements are widely used. Internet communication is technically carried out in written form, but its communication dynamics demonstrate the spontaneity, dialogicity, and emotionality inherent in oral speech, and in the Internet environment, users often use abbreviated units to quickly convey information. For example, abbreviations such as *info*, *msg*, and *pic* are widespread in English. Such units serve to speed up the communication process. At the same time, *emoji and graphic* symbols are also becoming an important component of discourse. Multimodal elements enhance the emotional and pragmatic content of the text. For example, on platforms such as Twitter[6] or Instagram[7], statements of the following form are common:

This decision is a disaster 😞

In this example, the abstract nouns “decision” and “disaster” are used as semantic units that evaluate a specific reality, and emoji enhance the emotional component of speech. Researchers emphasize that such a function of multimodal elements in discourse expands the semiotic scope of Internet communication[8]. Another important linguistic phenomenon observed in the process of digital communication is syntactic simplification. Due to the speed of Internet communication, users prefer simple sentence structures to complex syntactic structures. This process is sometimes associated with grammatical abbreviations and ellipsis. For example, in the discourse of *Reddit*[9] or *Twitter*[10], the following types of sentences are widespread:

Big problem here.

This sentence does not have the form of a complete sentence according to traditional grammatical norms, but in the discourse environment it has a full semantic content. This situation indicates that the environment plays a strong role in digital communication. Syntactic simplification increases the information density of discourse and facilitates rapid perception of speech[11].

In conclusion, the results of the study show that digital discourse, as an independent linguistic form of the modern communication system, significantly expands the functional capabilities of language units. The communicative conditions that have arisen in the Internet environment reshape the semantic and pragmatic properties of language, especially creating

the basis for the active use of abstract nouns. These units play an important role in expressing complex social realities in a concise and generalized manner, defining the semantic center of discourse, and conveying social evaluations.

In addition, the syntactic simplification, abbreviations, and multimodal elements inherent in digital communication demonstrate the dynamic and hybrid nature of discourse. As a result, language units become not only a communicative tool, but also a means of social identification and ideological expression. Therefore, the study of digital discourse is one of the relevant areas of modern linguistics, which allows for a deeper understanding of the interrelationships between language, society, and technology..

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